

Authors:

dr. Lejla I. Lerić

Hafiz Muhammad

Tariq

Emanuele Bertolani

Report

PR2

Definition of CREAM Creative
Writing Laboratories Model

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1 Introduction to CREAM

The CREAM project aims at stimulating the interest of school students in STEAM disciplines and will achieve this result by elaborating and testing a new model for teaching STEAM disciplines through the Creative Writing Laboratory technique by providing daily-life problems to be solved with a creative thinking approach and STEAM notions.

1.1 General Objectives of the CREAM project

The CREAM project aims at contributing to:

- expanding opportunities for promoting learning activities that focus the STEAM disciplines and help children learn through trial and error by experimenting and problem solving;
- acquiring scientific knowledge and actively participating in the innovation process of local communities;
- developing an integrative and collaborative approach (Creative Writing Laboratories - CWLs) to link STEAM to daily-life problems and enhance collaboration between formal, non-formal and informal science education providers, enterprises and civil society to enact the concept of open schooling;

1.2 Specific objectives of the CREAM Project

PR1: Explore what we know about STEAM innovative teaching approaches and initiatives using creative writing methodology at school.

This research activity resulted in the production of the Deliverable *PR1 "State of the Art analysis on STEAM creative teaching approaches and initiatives"*.

PR2: Codesign of CWLs concept

This will ensure the development of CREAM CWLs model (PR2).

PR3: Test and validate the CWLs model with the implementation of pilots in 4 countries (Italy (IT), Slovenia (SI), Greece (GR) and Poland (PL)) in PR3.

Pilots will involve all actors necessary for the implementation of the model: schools, companies, social enterprises and NGOs, universities and other education providers.

PR4: Storytelling (PR4)

At the end of each pilot, participants will be able to share

- stories on lessons learnt
- short video documentaries of the pilot experiences
- successful stories of scientists and innovative company founders etc.

Experience in CWLs pilots will have a direct impact on participants in making them “scientifically aware” or consider a scientific career. Students will be invited to explore different channels and means of artistic expression to propose their STEAM-based solutions to problems of public concern.

PR5: Set a sound exploitation and sustainability strategy tailored to end beneficiaries of the project: schools.

The aim is to provide a manual to replicate the CREAM experience and adopt, adapt and tailor the CWLs model.

PR6: Policy Paper, a set of recommendations for policy makers.

1.3 PR2 so far

PR2 was further subdivided into four different activities labelled A1 to A4. Of these, the first three have been completed successfully, whereas the last one is slated to be performed after the conclusion of the school Pilots.

PR2A1 co-design workshop & definition of the value proposition

A series of co-design workshops were conducted in each of the partner countries to brainstorm ideas and suggestions about the structure and operational characteristics of Creative Writing Laboratories applied to STEM subjects. All partners' contributions were then discussed during a dedicated TPM that took place in Reggio Emilia on the 21st of September 2022, and collated into a broad, workable concept and value proposition.

PR2A2 gender issues: strengthening the participation of female students

Issues pertaining to the under-representation of women in STEM fields have been analysed in a detailed desk research provided by DRPDNM. The research details social and cultural aspects of the present condition and outlines a set of recommendations to tackle them, with the aim of strengthening female's participation to, and representation in, STEM disciplines.

PR2A3 CREAM Creative Writing Laboratories Model

IEXs developed a model for the CWLs to be used in CREAM through a collaborative effort that involved all levels of the school's stakeholders: teachers, families and students. Over the course of 4 months, IEXs ran a series of dedicated workshops that resulted in the compilation of a document with theoretical guidelines and practical best practices for the implementation of CWLs in the context of the CREAM project.

PR2A4 Fine-tuning and validation of CREAM CWL model

The last step in PR2 will be implemented after the end of the Pilot Phase in July 2024.

1.4 Summary

This Deliverable compounds four separate contributions: a desk research on Gender issues penned by dr. Lejla I. Lerić from DRPDNM, a CWL Model report authored by IEXs' Hafiz Muhammad Tariq, plus additional contributions from *D2 - Results of Co-Design Workshops with Schools*, by Georgia Lascaris from Edumotiva, and a CWL Model Supplement by Emanuele Bertolani.

Each of these contributions is the culmination of the partners' activities in PR2A2 and PR2A3 respectively. They can be read as a balanced combination of theoretical knowledge and practical instructions derived from hands-on experience.

Dr. Lerić's work details a comprehensive outline of the phenomenon of female under-representation in STEM fields, analysing its sociological, cultural and educational factors before proposing practical steps to help reduce the gender gap.

Mr. Tariq's report exemplifies the process followed by IEXs in its experimentation with the CWL Model, from the setting up of preliminary workshops to clarify elements such as delivery methods, materials, internal and external actors' participation, evaluation etc., to the enactment of a CWL project proper and assessment thereof.

This section of the report also offers a wealth of information about implementation strategies, potential challenges and ways to overcome them.

Ms. Lascaris' contribution synthesises the content and the results of the co-design workshops conducted by each partner over the course of the operations of PR1.

Emanuele Bertolani's contribution aims at clarifying and simplifying the process of translating the theory of the CWL model into practice, and to help embed it within a storytelling-based context.

2 The STEM Gap

More girls are in school today than ever before, but they do not always have the same opportunities as boys to complete and benefit from an education of their choice. Too many girls and women are held back by biases, social norms and expectations influencing the quality of the education they receive and the subjects they study. They are particularly under-represented in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education, and consequently, in STEM careers.

Women make up only 28% of the workforce in science, technology, engineering and maths (STEM), and men vastly outnumber women majoring in most STEM fields in college

Giving women equal opportunities to pursue — and thrive in — STEM careers helps narrow the gender pay gap, enhances women’s economic security, ensures a diverse and talented STEM workforce and prevents biases in these fields and the products and services they produce.

2.1 Education and Training of Women

In 2007, under the German Presidency of the EU, the Council agreed on three EU-wide indicators, including two sub-indicators, to measure the progress in the EU on the implementation of the BPfA objectives in Area B: Education and Training of Women:

- B1. Proportion of female graduates and male graduates of all graduates in mathematics, the sciences and technical disciplines (tertiary education),
- B2. Employment rate of women and men (aged between 25 and 39 years; and aged between 40 and 64) by highest level of education attained,
- B3a. Proportion of female/male ISCED 5A graduates of all ISCED 5A graduates and proportion of female/male PhD graduates of all PhD graduates by broad field of study and total,
- B3b. Proportion of female and male academic staff differentiated by level of seniority and in total.

The proposal is to replace indicators B1, B3a and L3 (Area L: The Girl Child) with a new indicator:

- Proportion of women and men graduates in tertiary (ISCED Levels 5–8) and vocational (ISCED Levels 3–4) education and training in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) and in the field of education, health and welfare (EHW) – of all graduates in the study field.

2.1.1 Description of a new indicator

The indicator addresses gender segregation in fields of studies that are considered as key areas for the EU's smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. The Council Conclusions

on 'Enhancing the skills of women and men in the EU labour market' call for actions to 'combat gender discrimination, segregation and stereotypes in education, training, vocational training and career guidance; promote gender equality in schools, colleges and universities; encourage girls, boys, women and men from all backgrounds to choose educational fields and occupations in accordance with their abilities and skills, not based on gender stereotypes, and in particular by promoting women's and girls' access to educational fields and occupations inter alia in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM); encourage men and boys to study and work in fields such as social services, child care and long-term care' (Council of the European Union, 2017).

Table 1. Share of women within STEM and share of men within EHW study fields and by educational level – of all graduates in the field, EU average and Member States (2013–2015)

	STEM				EHW				
	Natural sciences, mathematics & statistics	ICT	Engineering, manufacturing & construction	Tertiary (ISCED 5-8)	Vocational (ISCED 35-45)	Health and welfare	Education	Tertiary (ISCED 5-8)	Vocational (ISCED 35-45)
AT	50%	13%	16%	26%	12%	24%	18%	22%	20%
BE	41%	6%	13%	26%	8%	21%	21%	23%	17%
BG	67%	41%	27%	38%	26%	33%	22%	27%	13%
CY	78%	34%	17%	39%	5%	34%	15%	21%	n.a.
CZ	59%	12%	18%	34%	11%	15%	15%	17%	8%
DE	48%	14%	14%	27%	10%	21%	19%	24%	19%
DK	50%	21%	22%	35%	10%	19%	31%	25%	14%
EE	79%	25%	29%	40%	36%	11%	7%	9%	12%
EL	53%	31%	19%	38%	12%	24%	17%	23%	19%
ES	53%	18%	22%	30%	14%	26%	22%	24%	26%
FI	56%	15%	19%	28%	17%	15%	20%	16%	16%
FR	47%	17%	16%	31%	11%	18%	24%	26%	9%
HR	64%	21%	18%	32%	16%	21%	5%	15%	22%
HU	52%	14%	16%	31%	9%	19%	17%	20%	14%
IE	51%	20%	15%	26%	20%	24%	27%	25%	16%
IT	56%	17%	22%	41%	17%	34%	7%	31%	26%
LT	59%	17%	18%	30%	9%	17%	19%	18%	17%
LU	48%	8%	12%	27%	11%	21%	32%	31%	24%
LV	61%	18%	19%	33%	10%	12%	8%	11%	6%
MT	53%	16%	16%	29%	16%	20%	24%	27%	9%
NL	43%	8%	12%	26%	7%	17%	20%	24%	12%
PL	71%	14%	25%	43%	11%	23%	15%	20%	15%
PT	62%	15%	27%	40%	17%	19%	19%	21%	14%
RO	65%	34%	34%	41%	33%	22%	6%	25%	15%
SE	52%	27%	20%	33%	11%	19%	20%	19%	23%
SI	61%	9%	16%	32%	9%	24%	12%	16%	21%
SK	64%	12%	18%	36%	10%	20%	19%	21%	13%
UK	53%	19%	23%	38%	n.a.	24%	24%	24%	n.a.
EU-28	54%	17%	19%	33%	13%	21%	19%	23%	16%

Note: On the basis of the currently applied ISCED-F 2013 classification. Data refer to tertiary education (ISCED 5–8) and VET (ISCED 35 & 45). STEM include Fo5 - Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics, Fo6 - Information and Communication Technologies, and Fo7 - Engineering, manufacturing and construction. EHW include Fo1 – Education and Fo9 - Health and welfare. Here and further on in regarding 2013-2015 data on education [educ_uoe_grado2], the following data limitations apply: BE: ISCED 35 2015 n.a. (2013/2014 average used); BG, EE, LT, RO, SK, FI: ISCED 5 n.a.; CZ, SI: ISCED 5 n.a.; IE: ISCED 35 & 45 n.a.; EL: 2015 n.a. (2013/2014 average used), ISCED 45 n.a.; ES: for ISCED 8: Fo5, Fo6 for 2013 and 2014, n.a. (2015 used), ISCED 45

The indicator enables the monitoring of progress regarding the gender balance of graduates from STEM and EHW study fields, including natural sciences, mathematics and statistics; information and communication technologies; engineering, manufacturing and construction; education; and health and welfare. Furthermore, the indicator makes it possible to take a closer look at the gender distribution of graduates across vocational education (ISCED 35–45) and tertiary education levels.

A typical STEM worker earns two-thirds more than those employed in other fields, according to Pew Research Center. And some of the highest-earning STEM occupations,

such as computer science and engineering, have the lowest percentages of women workers. The EU's commitment to the Beijing Platform for Action (BPfA) also marks an important step in recognising the need to advance gender equality in education, training and economy. The BPfA seeks to eliminate occupational segregation, especially by promoting equal participation of women in highly skilled jobs and senior management positions and by stimulating the diversification of occupational choices by both women and men (United Nations, 1995). A number of BPfA indicators on segregation in education, training and the labour market have been proposed by the German (2007), Slovenian (2008) and Belgium (2010) Presidencies, which were endorsed by the Council of the European Union. Following the request of the Estonian Presidency of the Council of the EU (2017), this report explores progress in overcoming educational and occupational gender segregation in the EU. It focuses on highly gender segregated study and employment fields, such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics or education, health and welfare. The research seeks to reveal which factors support or hinder segregation in education and the labour market, and what policies are addressing these issues at EU and Member State levels. The report analyses the trends and cross-country differences in women's and men's subject choices in education and training, transition from education to the labour market and employment conditions in gender-segregated fields, including pay gaps.

2.1.2 Key factors perpetuating gender STEM gaps:

Gender Stereotypes: STEM fields are often viewed as masculine, and teachers and parents often underestimate girls' maths abilities starting as early as preschool.

Male-Dominated Cultures: Because fewer women study and work in STEM, these fields tend to perpetuate inflexible, exclusionary, male-dominated cultures that are not supportive of or attractive to women and minorities.

Fewer Role Models: girls have fewer role models to inspire their interest in these fields, seeing limited examples of female scientists and engineers in books, media and popular culture. There are even fewer Black women role models in maths and science.

maths Anxiety: Teachers, who are predominantly women, often have maths anxiety they pass onto girls, and they often grade girls harder for the same work, and assume girls need to work harder to achieve the same level as boys.

By the time students reach college, women are significantly underrepresented in STEM majors — for instance, only around 21% of engineering majors are women and only around 19% of computer and information science majors are women.

Nearly 80% of the health care workforce are women, but only about 21% of health executives and board members are women, and only about a third of doctors. And, women are more highly represented in lower-paying fields, such as home health workers, nurses and the lower-paying specialties such as paediatricians.

38% of women who major in computers work in computer fields, and only 24% of those who majored in engineering work in the engineering field.

2.1.3 Girls' Achievements and Interest in maths and Science are shaped by the Environment around them

This report demonstrates the effects of societal beliefs and the learning environment on girls' achievements and interest in science and maths. One finding shows that when teachers and parents tell girls that their intelligence can expand with experience and learning, girls do better on maths tests and are more likely to say they want to continue to study maths in the future.

That is, believing in the potential for intellectual growth, in and of itself, improves outcomes.

This is true for all students, but it is particularly helpful for girls in mathematics, where negative stereotypes persist about their abilities. By creating a "growth mindset" environment, teachers and parents can encourage girls' achievement and interest in maths and science.

Most people associate science and maths fields with "male" and humanities and arts fields with "female," according to research examined in this report. Implicit bias is common, even among individuals who actively reject these stereotypes. This bias not only affects individuals' attitudes toward others but may also influence girls' and women's likelihood of cultivating their own interest in maths and science. Taking the implicit bias test at <https://implicit.harvard.edu> can help people identify and understand their biases so that they can work to compensate for them. Attracting and retaining more women in the STEM workforce will maximize innovation, creativity, and competitiveness.

2.2 Beliefs about Intelligence

Carol Dweck is a social and developmental psychologist at Stanford University. For 40 years she has studied the foundations of motivation. In an interview with AAUW, Dweck described how she first became interested in this topic: Since graduate school, I've been interested in how students cope with difficulty. Over the years it led me to understand that there were these whole frameworks that students brought to their achievement—that in one case made difficulty a terrible indictment but in the other case made difficulty a more exciting challenge. In one of my very first studies where I was giving failure problems, this little boy rubbed his hands together, smacked his lips, and said, "I love a challenge." And I thought, "Where is this kid from? Is he from another planet?" Either you cope with failure or you don't cope with failure, but to love it? That was something that was beyond my understanding, and I thought, "I'm going to figure out what this kid knows, and I'm going to bottle it." Over time I came to understand a framework in which you could relish something that someone else was considering a failure. Dweck's research provides evidence that a "growth mindset" (viewing intelligence as a changeable, malleable attribute that can be developed through effort) as opposed to a "fixed mindset" (viewing intelligence as an inborn, uncontrollable trait) is likely to lead to greater persistence in the face of adversity and ultimately success in any realm (Dweck & Leggett, 1988; Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck, 2006, 2008).

According to Dweck's research findings, individuals with a fixed mindset are susceptible to a loss of confidence when they encounter challenges, because they believe that if they are truly "smart," things will come easily to them. If they have to work hard at something, they tend to so often, when something comes quickly to a student, we say, "Oh, you're really good at this."

The message there is, “I think you’re smart when you do something that doesn’t require any effort or you haven’t challenged yourself.” Someone said to me recently, “In your culture, struggle is a bad word,” and I thought ... “That’s right.” We talk about it as an unfortunate thing, but when you think about a career in science or maths or anything, of course you struggle. That’s the name of the game! If you’re going to discover something new or invent something new, it’s a struggle. So I encourage educators to celebrate that, to say:

“Who had a fantastic struggle? Tell me about your struggle!”

—Carol Dweck questions their abilities and loses confidence, and they are likely to give up because they believe they are “not good” at the task and, because their intelligence is fixed, will never be good at it.

Individuals with a growth mindset, on the other hand, show a far greater belief in the power of effort, and in the face of difficulty, their confidence actually grows because they believe they are learning and getting smarter as a result of challenging themselves (see figure 14). Dweck and her colleagues found that students—in both middle school and college—are about equally divided between the two mindsets.

The significance of an individual’s mindset often does not emerge until she or he faces challenges. In a supportive environment such as elementary school, students with a belief in fixed intelligence may do just fine; however, upon encountering the challenges of middle school, differences are likely to emerge between students with a fixed mindset about intelligence and those who believe that intelligence can increase with effort.

Dweck’s research is particularly relevant to women in STEM, because she and her colleagues have found that for both middle school and college students, a growth mindset protects girls and women from the influence of the stereotype that girls are

not as good as boys at maths (Good et al., 2003, 2009). If a girl with a fixed mindset encounters a challenging task or experiences a setback in maths, she is more likely to believe the stereotype that girls are not as good as boys in maths.

2.2.1 Stereotype

Negative stereotypes about girls' and women's abilities in mathematics and science persist despite girls' and women's considerable gains in participation and performance in these areas during the last few decades. Two stereotypes are prevalent: girls are not as good as boys in maths, and scientific work is better suited to boys and men. Stereotype threat may help explain the discrepancy between female students' higher grades in maths and science and their lower performance on high-stakes tests in these subjects, such as the SAT-maths (SAT-M) and AP calculus exam. Additionally, stereotype threat may also help explain why fewer girls than boys express interest in and aspirations for careers in mathematically demanding fields. Girls may attempt to reduce the likelihood that they will be judged through the lens of negative stereotypes by saying they are not interested and by avoiding these fields.

2.2.2 Four Main Reasons Why There Is a Lack of Women in STEM

While there is indeed an increase in the number of women who study STEM programs in college and take STEM jobs, facts on women in STEM reveal that their percentage in these fields is actually dropping. It is therefore important for education systems to intervene to rekindle or maintain girls' and young women's aspirations for a STEM career. Encouraging girls to pursue an education and career in the STEM field is

important not only to remedy the lack of graduates in the STEM job market, but also to diversify and enrich perspectives to ensure that researchers, entrepreneurs, and leaders in STEM tackle the complex problems facing the world from diverse viewpoints. Reaching gender parity in STEM also serves two of UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goals ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and achieving gender equality. Similarly, the United Nations sees gender equality 'not only as a fundamental human right, but a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world.

Not only fewer women opt for STEM education and careers but are also more likely to leave and get paid less. Considering the fact that there is a huge emphasis on gender equality throughout the United States, a lack of women in STEM does not make much sense.

The Bureau of Labor Statistics indicates that there is plenty of need for more workers in STEM. Even though STEM salaries are some of the highest, we have a shortage of STEM professionals. We need at least a million more STEM professionals right now, and this number is only expected to increase over the coming decades.

Parents also believe girls do not perform as well as boys in maths. When they offer help to their daughters with their maths homework, this help is perceived by girls as an indication of their lower academic performance than boys' (Bhanot & Jovanovic, 2005). When talking to the parents of STEM-aspiring students, the parents of male students are more likely to have university aspirations for their children compared to the parents of female students (Lloyd et al., 2018).

2.2.3 Why there is a lack of women in STEM

The Environment Shapes Girls' Interest and Motivation in STEM

Girls have an interest in STEM. Well, middle school girls have an interest in STEM. Some sources indicate that about 74% of middle school girls have an interest in STEM subjects. Yet, data from Microsoft shows that this interest drops when they reach high school.

A report from the American Association of University Women (AAUW) shows that the learning environment and social belief system affect girls' interest and achievements in STEM subjects. Findings revealed that girls who believe that experience and learning expanded intelligence were more likely to do better on maths tests. They also expressed more interest in pursuing science subjects in the future. The opposite belief achieved the contrary effect. Interestingly, fewer women enrol in higher STEM education tracks in countries with high gender equality, like Norway and Finland, than in countries with lower gender equality, like Algeria and Iran (Stoet & Geary, 2018). Women in societies with high gender equality and with more economic opportunities possibly do not suffer negative consequences for choosing a non-STEM career and can choose one according to their personal interests and strengths. In other words, women might be choosing non-STEM fields not because they think they do badly in STEM, but simply because they do better in social sciences.

Age

Age is a critical factor for STEM interventions. Although early interventions are important, the age of 12 seems to be a critical point (González-Pérez, de Cabo, & Sáinz,

2020; Sáinz & Eccles, 2012) when girls start losing interest in STEM and confidence in their STEM skills. skills. A

Microsoft-commissioned survey found that girls in Europe become interested in STEM subjects around the age of 11 and lose interest mostly by the age of 15. Thus, a “growth mindset” can have a massive impact on whether girls will keep their interest and motivation in STEM or go for more “feminine” careers instead.

Another study performed in Europe showed that how women are treated in a specific country has a direct correlation with how well girls perform on maths tests.

Girls from countries like Sweden and Iceland where society treats women more like equals did as well as or even better than boys on maths tests. Meanwhile, girls from countries like Turkey where gender discrimination is greater showed worse maths tests results than boys.

Social Bias Affect Women’s Progress and Career Choices

Research shows that people view STEM fields as masculine up to this day. Society views women in science and engineering jobs as less competent than men unless they are showing considerable success. And even then colleges, Universities, and Workplaces Aren’t Making Enough Necessary Changes to Accommodate Female Students.

When it comes to middle school, there are plenty of options and support for girls to develop STEM skills. There are science classes and science fairs that are eager to involve girls.

However, beyond middle school, this support diminishes and so does the number of women in STEM. Fewer girls keep their interest and motivation in science subjects in

high school and enroll in STEM degrees. This results in fewer female graduates in science, technology and engineering fields. e view them as less likable individuals.

Lack of Role Models

Because of the lack of women in STEM, young girls, students, and college graduates do not have many role models that can inspire them to opt for STEM jobs. Stereotypes and biases also shape the public's opinion on what women in STEM should be or look like.

Labour markets and educational choices

Wiswall and Zafar (2018) investigate the relationship between gender preferences for the workplace and gender choice of education fields and jobs. The authors survey undergraduate students at New York University with hypothetical questions on job choices. Gender differences exist in workplace preferences among these students. Males prefer jobs with higher growth rates in earnings, whereas females prefer more secure jobs and jobs with greater flexibility. Combined with the follow-up surveys four years later regarding the actual choices of majors and jobs, the authors estimate a strong and systematic link between job preferences and decisions in choosing majors and jobs, through a choice model. Specifically, the authors estimate that, for a university major, one standard deviation increase in the perceived probability of dismissal in future jobs drives 5% of women and 4% of men away from a major, and one standard deviation increase in the perceived average earnings from future jobs attracts 5% more women and 16% more men to a major. The authors also show that the within-field gender difference in jobs, compared with the gender difference in fields, drives the gender gap in earnings.

Cultural context

The role of country-level culture has been examined by Nollenberger et al. (2016), who study the relationship between culture and the gender gap in mathematics. The authors use four waves of PISA data, which provide culture-neutral maths assessment results for second-generation immigrants across 35 countries. An individual-level multivariate model regressing maths test scores on gender, culture and other controls estimates the relationship between culture and the maths gender gap. The results show that the gender gap in mathematics decreases for students with ancestry from countries with greater gender equality.

2.3 Women in STEM

Dr. Jodie Ward is the Team Leader of NSW Health Pathology's Specialist DNA Laboratory at the Forensic & Analytical Science Service and she is passionate about using forensic science to help make a difference to people's lives.

Having established this laboratory in 2015, she has since created a specialist DNA service for the identification of human remains, being used nationally by the police and armed forces.

Jodie previously worked for the NSW Police and Australian Federal Police. She is also a Forensic Biology Lecturer at the Canberra Institute of Technology and supervises postgraduate research in her role as Adjunct Professional Associate at the University of Canberra.

Sanam is a trained Molecular Pharmacologist. She completed her undergraduate studies at the University of Glasgow, graduating in 2004 with a M.Sci (Honours) in Genetics.

She has trained in some of the world's leading laboratories researching G protein-coupled receptors. Her prestigious PhD studentship was co-funded by the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council and GlaxoSmithKline.

Following postdoctoral positions with Almirall and Prof Kevin Pflieger's group at the University of Western Australia, Sanam moved to the University of Adelaide. Working

with Prof Mark Hutchinson's Neuroimmune Pharmacology group and the Australian Research Council Centre of Excellence for Nanoscale BioPhotonics (CNBP), she has widened her research interests to include neuroimmunology.

Hannah is an Adelaide born and educated, internationally trained, emerging research leader based at the University of Adelaide, at the Centre for Nanoscale Biophotonics, Robinson Research Institute. Her research interests are embedded in women's pregnancy health, with a particular focus on the first days and weeks of pregnancy.

Members of her team work on the basic biological processes of conception, novel technology development for the IVF industry, through behavioural and social research exploring how to communicate fertility messages to diverse audiences.

Associate Professor Muirean Irish is an ARC Future Fellow in the School of Psychology and Brain & Mind Centre, University of Sydney.

Muireann says her field of research is the cognitive neuroscience of memory, but she is particularly fascinated by how humans remember the past and imagine the future, and how these capacities are disrupted in dementia.

Originally from Ireland, she completed a Bachelor degree and PhD in Psychology at Trinity College Dublin, before relocating to Australia and receiving continuous funding from the ARC since 2013 (ARC DECRA, ARC Future Fellowship).

2.3.1 Strategies for Increasing Girls' Participation in STEM

Show the Range of STEM Opportunities

To encourage more girls and girls of colour to participate in STEM studies, schools can be more explicit about the range of STEM areas. Schools can also deliberately infuse stories of women's contributions in the STEM fields and how it benefits girls to pursue advanced coursework in this area. This helps students see themselves in such fields and gives them a chance to find the right fit for themselves.

Encourage STEM Investigations

Teachers can encourage students to conduct STEM investigations based on their own interests and expertise, particularly related to issues in their communities. This can take the form of individual projects or larger project-based learning programs. The key is to demonstrate the application of STEM to real-world questions.

Provide STEM Mentoring Opportunities

It is important for girls to connect with successful women in STEM careers. Reaching out to female STEM mentors provides access to professionals who can answer field-related questions. For example, IDRA's Texas Chief Science Office program that the IDRA EAC-South is managing in Texas connects students with STEM professionals within

their community and empowers students to pursue their STEM interests. Students create year-long STEM action plans in their schools and pursue them to completion throughout the school year.

Explore STEM Careers and Studies

STEM is a vast landscape of opportunity, and there are many career pathways and college programs to share with students. Elementary school teachers can begin the process by helping students make connections between STEM classes and future career options.

Many programs outside of school interest young students and engage the whole family. Museums, zoos, scouting organizations, and STEM clubs can offer workshops and events for students. Having a strong knowledge base in STEM topics gives students the opportunity to approach higher level coursework in high school with confidence.

Nurture Family Engagement in STEM Learning

Dr. Linda Kekelis (2017), founder of Techbridge Girls, offers the following suggestions for engaging with families for STEM connections.

2.4 Conclusions

Gender Issues pertaining to female participation to STEM fields are a multi-faceted, complex phenomenon that requires the consideration of multiple levels of analysis to be properly conceptualised and tackled.

Sociological, cultural and educational aspects can boost or inhibit female participation in STEM fields. A good example is the persistent stereotype that sees girls as somehow inherently less talented in Maths, or less prone to engage with it. An equally persistent stereotype considers girls as intrinsically more interested in Human Sciences rather than hard ones, and their participation in the former is encouraged more readily than in the latter, particularly in cultures that tend to be more reliant on traditional values.

The environment, specifically in the form of the family orientation towards or against female participation in STEM fields, and the availability of inspirational role-models are also identified as key ingredients to the overall objective of strengthening the role of women and girls in STEM.

Encouraging greater female participation in STEM necessitates:

- the creation of a range of opportunities, and the active promotion of those opportunities already in existence across the educational levels.
- effectively communicating the possibilities offered by a career in STEM fields.
- identifying and showing valid role-models
- eliciting families to embrace a broader view of the educational range available for girls.

The results of the trials conducted by IEXs seem to indicate that CWL applied to STEM possesses excellent educational potential. However, tapping into that potential

requires a significant amount of preparatory work and the adoption of mitigating strategies to manage potential risks.

The advantages of the CWL should be communicated properly and effectively to all stakeholders, together with the associated costs. CWLs require the adoption of a new mindset from teachers, families and students alike. This mindset change should be solidified by dedicated training before the beginning of the activities, to enable teachers to perform their tasks with the necessary confidence.

The recommendations can be broadly summarised as follows:

- Students should be provided with a problem, a set of parameters (duration, dos and don'ts, etc...), and an output to produce in response to the problem.
- Evaluation should be based on pre-established parameters and should be individual, even in the case of group work.
- Technology, physical activity and current events should be built into the CWL whenever possible, to maximise students' engagement and willingness to participate.
- The model should be kept flexible enough to adapt to the specific requirements of a given setting.
- Implementers should strive to set up the CWL so that its results are achievable and measurable, as this encourages participation in students and facilitates the acceptance of the CWL Model in institutions.

The results described in this deliverable will come to fruition during the subsequent Pilot Phase of the CREAM Project.

3 Co-design workshops

3.1 Introduction

The CREAM project aims to stimulate school students' interest in STEAM disciplines by developing and testing a new model for teaching STEAM disciplines using the **Creative Writing Laboratory** (CWL) technique, which will provide daily-life problems to be solved using a creative thinking approach and STEAM notions. The CWL model will be implemented and tested in four pilot projects in schools and STEAM centers in Italy, Poland, Slovenia, and Greece.

IESX, EDUMOTIVA, GRMNM and ZSO made contact with schools and held several workshops between October and December 2022 to present the CREAM project, investigate their needs, and ensure that the project will meet their expectations.

Edumotiva's "D2 Results of Co-Design Workshops with Schools" report summarizes feedback from the initial contacts and workshops held at both partners' and external schools between October and December 2022.

3.2 Workshops Overview

The main goal of the workshops that were conducted in schools between October and December 2022, was to present the CREAM project to all stakeholders involved and lay the groundwork for future collaboration.

Each of the participating organizations (IEXS in Italy, GRMNM in Slovenia, ZSO in Poland, and EDUMOTIVA in Greece) held a number of meetings and workshops with their schools to

- present the CREAM project
- explore the interest of Headmasters, teachers, and students in participating in STEAM activities
- brainstorm activities that could be implemented
- explore the way those activities may or may not be included in the school's curricula.

The workshops and meetings did not adhere to a formal methodology (figure 1). Instead, each partner devised its own strategy (brainstorming, informal meetings, workshops, focus groups, co-design) for gathering the necessary information and reporting it in a feedback report.

All partners, however, completed the same Feedback Form questionnaire developed by Edumotiva in the framework of the D2 Results of Co-Design Workshops with Schools.

3.3 Co-design activities

To encourage higher student and teacher participation, most of the schools chose to integrate the CREAM pilots in their curriculum.

Organization Name	Integrated into the school's Curriculum	Extracurricular Implementation
EDUMOTIVA	✓	
IEXS	✓	
GRMNM	✓	
ZSO		✓

Greek schools intend to incorporate the CREAM pilots within the national schools' curriculum in a flexible, interdisciplinary way by combining a number of school subjects (Skills Labs, Computer Science, Art, Environmental Education, Maths, Physics ..) and involving teachers of different fields (classroom teacher, computer science teacher, art teacher, foreign language teacher...). It has also been proposed to incorporate the CREAM pilots into an eTwinning 2023-2024 project with the participation of partners' schools in Europe. Each school's coordinating teacher is highly specialised in scientific and STEAM disciplines and will serve as the primary point of contact for Edumotiva and the other teachers. Furthermore, because the environment and climate change are well-known topics among teachers, the CREAM project can be more easily introduced to them.

The Creative Writing Labs activities will also be integrated into the **IEXS school** curriculum. An iteration of the basic CWL model will be implemented in class and the

results will be shared among all partners. The structure of the CWL model will include the following parameters and details:

- lesson plan
- useful links
- argument details
- storytelling content
- Goals
- maximum and minimum objectives
- Timeline
- and finally the output required from the students.

The final workshop will also involve some external companies.

GRMNM school will also integrate the CWL activities into its curriculum. The supervising teachers will determine whether the business ideas are feasible and marketable, as well as any links to STEM disciplines, such as quality control, organic products, and environmental protection, among other things.

ZSO School plans to apply the CWL to extracurricular activities as an inspiring pilot project with the help of creative teachers and eager students who are willing to try out innovative pedagogical techniques.

3.4 Proposed Activities

3.4.1 Feedback from IEXS

During the workshops between the partners and the schools, numerous STEM activities with teachers, students and parents were brainstormed and co-designed, all tailored to the needs of each school.

More specifically, IEXS students will investigate real-world environmental issues such as:

- global warming
- benefits of green economies
- how new technologies such as artificial intelligence can be used to solve global problems
- how DNA reformation and gene therapy can treat disorders and diseases

3.4.2 Feedback from Edumotiva

The main goal for Greek schools is to help students develop 21st-century, digital, and environmental competencies through STEAM activities, according to the *European Digital Competence Framework 2.2 for Citizens* and the *European Green-Comp framework for sustainability competencies*. Students will investigate the relationship between climate change and biodiversity in their city and propose sustainable solutions. Biodiversity will be a key aspect of their project, as they will investigate the flora and fauna of their area using Artificial Intelligence powered Citizen Science tools, as well as the role of pollinators, particularly bees, in ensuring the survival and diversity of food crops and medicinal plants. Activities will include, among others:

- the construction of bee houses for single bees, bee gardens, sensor-equipped robot bees

- the exploration or development of AI applications that can assist beekeepers in better monitoring their hives.

3.4.2 Feedback from GRMNM

Students participated in workshops where they developed business concepts related to agriculture and farming. In order to put products like growing microgreens, butter-milk with herbs, therapeutic camping, and traditional flatbread straight from the field on the market, the students suggested looking into preparation techniques. They will learn how to be entrepreneurial so they may secure new jobs on their farms. In order to compete in contests for start-ups in their town, students will work in teams of two or three and create a business plan with all the expenditures and revenues that are anticipated. Even if they do not receive the grant for their business, they will have learned how to prepare a business proposal for future ideas.

3.4.3 Feedback from ZSO

After a series of workshops with teachers, students, and parents at the ZSO school in the middle of December, a meeting with WUT was held online. After that, teachers and students collaborated to develop some ideas for creative writing activities. First, a list of current issues should be presented to the students, who must select one to elaborate on later. Then, the students will create a fictional or crime story based on a specific topic and will use several applications to present the story, like creating a video to act out the narrative. The film will be used to demonstrate the experiment's results in an innovative manner. This way, different fields of study can be combined, such as creative writing on some technological issues or global problems, with some unusual experiments, and then using some IT technologies to film all of the work.

In short: 1. Choosing the subject, 2. Looking into the issue, 3. Writing a crime story about it, 4. Present it during workshops, 5. Filming it 6. Using some IT skills to edit the film, 7. Present the film.

3.5 Conclusions

In November and December 2022, IEXS, EDUMOTIVA, ZSO, and WRMNM held a number of workshops and meetings with schools, mostly with teachers and students, to introduce the CREAM project and the CWL model. Furthermore, in the near future, all schools will reach out to other interested parties, such as parents and external partners, (Municipalities, Universities, Educational Providers, Companies, Social Enterprises NGOs...). The majority of schools intend to involve more than two student teams in the CWL and have tailored their activities to students in the age groups of 12 to 14, 14 to 16, and 16 to 18.

The STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) disciplines will all be included in the activities, along with some non-STEM ones like the arts, social studies, and humanities. The STEAM activities that have been proposed by schools are related to real-world challenges like those outlined in the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (Climate Change, Life on Land, Quality Education, Gender Equality, Good Health and Well-Being, Zero Hunger, Affordable and Clean Energy), and they will be supported by teachers from various disciplines, mostly by teachers with a science and computer science background.

Some of the consortium schools will incorporate the CLW model into their curriculum in order to increase student and teacher participation, while others will use it as a pilot project in extracurricular activities.

4 CWL Model

4.1 Introduction

To implement the CREAM project's idea of curricular and non-curricular activities organised in schools by a group of stakeholders, a series of workshops were conducted among selected teachers, parents, school management, and other primary and secondary stakeholders to introduce them to the project. The IEXS was able to achieve six such events where different participants had taken part.

The workshops aimed at brainstorming the active stakeholders of the education system such as teachers, and other stakeholders like students, parents, school management, and local industry partners. In subsequent workshops, the stakeholders were able to give their feedback for the improvement of the CWL model.

The objective of these activities was to discuss STEAM problems and involvement of storytelling methods to enhance the interest of students in science fields and provide them with better and easier ways of learning. This objective was concluded with the creation of a CWL model, where STEM concepts are applied to the contents of writing to stimulate students' imagination and creativity to solve problems of public concern.

4.2 Main objectives of the workshops conducted by IEXS

4.2.1 Workshop on "Existing Teaching Methods in STEAM Education" and "The CWL Model"

- Participants discussed project-based learning, problem-based learning, game-based learning, and storytelling in education.
- The group reviewed the key principles and parameters of the CWL Model.
- The role of creative writing, STEAM subject focus, and the importance of Art were highlighted.
- Planning and preparation aspects, classroom management and instruction, and assessment and evaluation of the CWL Model were discussed.

4.2.2 Workshop on "Examples of the CWL Model in Practice"

- Participants were divided into three groups focusing on creative writing in science class, storytelling in maths class, or integrating the arts in technology class.
- Each group identified objectives of incorporating a given skill into the class and discussed how the CWL Model can be used to achieve these objectives.
- Specific examples of how to integrate the given skill into the lesson were provided.

4.2.3 Workshop on "Assessing the Effectiveness of the CWL Model: Stakeholders Feedback and Beyond"

- The importance of evaluating teaching methods and models to improve education was discussed.
- Survey results were analysed, including key findings and trends, student feedback, and perceptions of the CWL Model.

- The CWL Model was compared with other teaching methods such as project-based learning, problem-based learning, and game-based learning.

4.2.4 Workshop on "Integrating Technology into the CWL Model"

- Participants discussed the importance of technology in education.
- Challenges of integrating technology into the CWL Model were identified.
- Specific examples of how to use technology to enhance the CWL Model were provided.

4.2.5 Workshop on "Implementing the CWL Model in the Classroom"

- Key considerations in planning and preparation were discussed.
- Classroom management and instruction were addressed.
- Challenges that may arise were identified.
- Best practices and strategies for success in the CWL Model were shared.

4.2.6 Workshop on "Developing Assessment Tools for the CWL Model"

- The importance of assessment and evaluation in education was discussed.
- Assessment and evaluation aspects of the CWL Model were reviewed.
- Specific assessment tools for the CWL Model were developed.

The detailed reports of each workshop are attached below in the appendix for the reference.

4.3 CWL model lesson

The following is an example of the CWL Model, designed for students of IT. The lesson was created through a collaborative effort of primary and secondary stakeholders, ensuring that students' needs were met using this innovative approach. Inputs were gathered from all stakeholders to develop this model, which can be applied to all subjects and school levels due to its unique and practical characteristics.

The model employs storytelling as a bridge to connect science and arts, which facilitates real-world problem-solving and increases student engagement. The CWL Model can be implemented in both curricular and extracurricular activities, with the amount of time devoted to it being subject to the discretion of teachers and students. The organisation of the curriculum's content for the school year may also determine the extent of the CWL Model's use.

4.3.1 CWL (Creative Writing Laboratory):

DEADLINE: [15-02-2023]

TOTAL TIME: 8 Hours

IMPORTANT LINKS FOR HELP:

1. Codecademy: <https://www.codecademy.com/>
2. Khan Academy: <https://www.khanacademy.org/computing/computer-science>
3. W3Schools: <https://www.w3schools.com/>

SUBJECTS AND TOPICS:

1. Algorithms and Data Structures

2. Web Development
3. Database Management

GOALS:

The goal of this CWL is to provide students with a hands-on approach to learn and understand the basics of computer science and its applications. The students will work on projects that will help them to develop their coding skills, creativity, and problem-solving abilities.

OBJECTIVES:

1. Basic Level: Design and develop a simple website using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript.
2. Intermediate Level: Create an algorithm to solve a specific problem using a programming language of choice (e.g., Python, Java).
3. Advanced Level: Develop a full-stack web application that includes a database, user authentication, and a user-friendly interface.

OUTPUT:

1. Website/Algorithm/Web Application
2. Presentation explaining the project and its features

TIMELINE:

1. Introduction and orientation to the CWL - [09-02-2-23]
2. Project planning and design - [10-02-2-23]

3. Coding and implementation - [12-02-2-23]
4. Final presentations and evaluations - [13-02-2-23]

GROUP OR INDIVIDUAL ACTIVITY:

This activity can be either group-based or individual-based, depending on the preference of the students and the teacher's discretion.

EVALUATION:

The students' projects will be evaluated based on the following criteria:

1. Creativity and originality
2. Technical accuracy
3. Presentation and communication skills

NOTE:

1. Each student is expected to work on a unique project, and plagiarism will not be tolerated.
2. The students are encouraged to seek help from the teacher, online resources, and their peers, but the final output should be their original work.

4.3.2 CWL model description

The CWL (Creative Writing Laboratory) Method is an innovative approach to teaching STEAM subjects. The main goal of this method is to provide students with hands-on experience in science subjects and to help them understand the fundamental concepts.

The CWL method is designed to provide students with different levels of difficulty, from basic to advanced. This allows students of different backgrounds to choose a project that matches their abilities and interests. As per the example provided by the lesson presented above, the basic level objective is to design and develop a simple website using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. The intermediate level objective is to create an algorithm to solve a specific problem using a programming language of choice. The advanced level objective is to develop a full-stack web application that includes a database, user authentication, and a user-friendly interface.

The CWL method provides students with a set timeline for the activity, which includes an introduction and orientation to the CWL, project planning and design and implementation, and final presentations and evaluations. The students can choose to work either in a group or individually, depending on their preference and the teacher's discretion.

The students' projects can be evaluated based on creativity and originality, technical accuracy, and presentation and communication skills. The students are encouraged to seek help from the teacher, online resources, and their peers, but the final output should be their original work.

The CWL method provides students with important sources and links for help so the students' productivity and creativity can be increased. These resources allow students to expand their knowledge and improve their science skills.

The CWL Method is a valuable tool for teaching computer science, technology, and overall STEAM subjects. The method allows students to choose a project that matches their abilities and interests and provides them with important resources for learning

and improving their skills. The CWL method is an effective way to teach students the skills they need to succeed not only in the Arts but in the technology field as well.

4.3.3 CWL Evaluation Methods

The participants came up with some ideas and provided valuable feedback for the creation of an effective CWL evaluation method. The evaluation answer highlights several key objectives related to the implementation of the CWL Model in the classroom. The first objective is to bring innovation to the classroom and enhance the final output of students. This includes the establishment of criteria for evaluating individual and group work, with parameters that vary depending on the lesson and activity. For example, creativity, content preparation, didactic ability, public speaking, and more.

Another objective is to incorporate student self-evaluation at the end of the lesson, which can be confirmed or modified by the teacher. This includes evaluating creativity, content, presentation skills, digital competency, graphic design, behaviour (listening and collaboration skills), and didactic congruence (timeliness).

To ensure the effectiveness of the CWL Model, the third objective is to administer tests that assess the student's didactic competencies. The fourth objective is to obtain student feedback through a general statistical evaluation of the activity and the applied method.

Lastly, the fifth objective involves using the established evaluation criteria to assess the students' performance in terms of creativity, content preparation, presentation skills, digital competency, graphic design, behaviour, and didactic congruence. By

accomplishing these objectives, educators can ensure the effective implementation of the CWL Model and promote better learning outcomes for their students.

This CWL model would be implemented for six months in IEXS. Afterwards, a survey would be conducted from the stakeholders who were part of this project throughout the same period.

4.4 Implementation of the Creative Writing Laboratory and Challenges

The Creative Writing Laboratory (CWL) is a new approach to learning that aims to enhance students' creativity, emotional intelligence, and engagement in the writing process. Despite the benefits of the CWL model, there are several challenges that need to be addressed to ensure its success in schools and educational institutions.

4.4.1 Challenges

1. Problem Solving with Examples without a Solution: the CWL provides students with challenges that require creative solutions. However, some examples may not have a definite solution, which can create frustration and disorientation in the students.
2. Student Interest: maintaining student interest is crucial for the success of the CWL. Teachers must be able to present challenging topics and activities to keep students engaged.
3. Different Obstacles: students may encounter various obstacles in the learning process, such as resistance to innovation, fear of creativity, and lack of time.
4. Changing the Way of Learning in Schools: implementing the CWL requires schools and educational institutions to be willing to change their traditional teaching methods, which can generate resistance from teachers, managers, and parents.
5. Involvement of People: the CWL requires the active participation of teachers, parents, and students. Engaging all stakeholders can be a challenge, especially if some individuals struggle to understand or learn.
6. Developing Emotional Intelligence: the CWL aims to develop students' emotional intelligence, which requires time, effort, and resources.

To overcome these challenges, schools and educational institutions must be prepared to invest in training, customised lesson plans, and in the integration of innovative technologies. Teachers, managers, and parents must be open to the CWL model and its benefits. The active involvement of all stakeholders, along with the creation of a safe and positive learning environment, is essential for the success of the CWL in schools and educational institutions.

While the implementation of the CWL model in schools and educational institutions poses several challenges, the benefits it provides to students are invaluable. With the active involvement of all stakeholders, and the integration of innovative technologies, the CWL can revolutionise the approach to learning in schools and educational institutions.

4.4.2 Success strategies in CWL Model

- Method readiness: openness and willingness of teachers, leaders, and parents to adopt the CWL method is necessary for success.
- Training: proper training for teachers is essential for successful implementation of the CWL method.
- Voluntary participation: encouraging students' voluntary participation in the learning process can increase their interest and involvement.

4.4.3 Proposed improvements for the CWL

- Integrating video and storytelling: the use of video and storytelling can enhance the engagement and challenge level of the CWL program for students.

- Review of previous lessons: including moments of review of previous lessons can ensure better understanding of the subject matter.
- Increase field trips: field visits and hands-on experiences can enhance student learning and interest in the CWL program.
- Incorporate current affairs into lessons: integrating current affairs into lessons can help students connect the CWL program to the real world and develop a deeper understanding of the topics covered.
- Engage motor skills: including motor activities in the CWL program can aid in student learning and development of coordination and body awareness.
- Combine the CWL with other learning models: combining the CWL program with other teaching models, such as project-based learning, can ensure comprehensive training and a balanced approach to education.

4.4.4 Key factors for the growth and success of the CWL

- Resilience: both students and teachers need to exhibit resilience to overcome the challenges and obstacles they may encounter during the implementation of the CWL.
- Freedom of choice in topics: allowing students to choose topics of interest to them can increase their motivation and involvement in the learning process.
- Convincing schools to use the CWL: convincing schools and educational institutions of the benefits and effectiveness of the CWL is critical to ensure its widespread adoption.
- Application of the CWL in different areas: to ensure the success of the CWL, it is important to apply it to a wide range of educational areas and contexts.

- Continuing education: regular training for teachers is essential to ensure that the CWL is successfully implemented and continues to evolve over time.
- Personalization of lessons: adapting the CWL to the specific needs and interests of students can ensure more effective and engaging learning experiences.

4.4.5 Tips for enhancing the efficiency of the CWL for students and teachers

- Active listening: teachers should actively listen to students, taking their needs and interests into account in the learning process.
- Feedback: gathering feedback from students at the end of lessons can help teachers understand which aspects of the CWL are working well and which require improvement.
- Clear timing: establishing clear timing for activities and lessons can ensure that the learning process is well-organised and efficient.
- Teacher-student relationship: building a relationship of trust and openness between teachers and students can improve the quality of learning and the effectiveness of the CWL.
- Use of technology: the adoption of digital technologies and platforms can improve the accessibility and effectiveness of the CWL, allowing for greater customization and flexibility.
- Building basic models: incorporating hands-on activities, such as building basic models, can provide a more engaging and tactile learning experience for students.
- Collaboration: encouraging collaboration and teamwork among students can foster a sense of community and encourage the development of social skills.

Creative incentives: offering creative incentives, such as prizes or recognition, can motivate students and increase their interest and engagement in the CWL."

4.4.6 Suggestions for future implementations of the CWL in schools and educational institutions:

- Clearly communicate the benefits: school principals, teachers, and parents should be presented with the benefits of the CWL to increase support and willingness to adopt the new method.
- Use visual and interactive materials: incorporating visual and interactive materials can enhance the CWL, making it more engaging and challenging for students.
- Integrate current events and technology: integrating current events, creativity, and technology into CWL lessons can help keep students interested and engaged.
- Provide emotional intelligence training: providing specific emotional intelligence training can help teachers develop the skills needed to support students in the CWL.
- Customise the model: tailoring the CWL to the specific needs and interests of students and schools can ensure more effective and engaging learning.

4.4.7 Strategies for Disseminating and Implementing the CWL in the Educational Sector

- Global Promotion: widely promoting the CWL through various channels can increase awareness and generate interest in the method across different regions and countries.
- Testimonials and Success Stories: sharing success stories and testimonials of those who have already implemented the CWL can inspire and encourage other schools and institutions to adopt the method.
- Introducing the Method at a Young Age: introducing the CWL in elementary and middle schools can help students develop creative writing skills from an early age, leading to better outcomes in the future.
- Clear Communication: communicating the benefits and effectiveness of the CWL in a clear and compelling manner is crucial for its widespread adoption.
- Demonstrating Positive Results: demonstrating the success of the CWL through measurable results can encourage other schools and institutions to implement the method.
- Safe and Feasible Models: developing and sharing realistic baseline models of the CWL can facilitate its implementation and adoption by schools and educational institutions, ensuring its sustainability and effectiveness.

4.4.8 Strengths of the CWL model

- Creativity: the CWL fosters creativity in students, enabling them to explore new ideas and think innovatively.
- Emotional Intelligence: the CWL promotes the development of emotional intelligence by helping students understand and manage their own emotions

and those of others, which is a crucial aspect of their personal and social development.

- Engagement and Interest: the CWL increases students' engagement and interest in the learning process, making lessons more challenging, relevant and enjoyable.
- Freedom of Expression: the CWL offers students the opportunity to express themselves freely and to share their ideas without restrictions, promoting communication, critical thinking, and collaboration.
- Personalization: the CWL can be tailored to the specific needs and interests of students, ensuring more effective and engaging learning and greater individualization of the learning process.
- Motor Engagement: incorporating motor activities into CWL lessons can help students learn better and develop important skills such as coordination and body awareness, contributing to their physical and cognitive development.

4.4.9 Weaknesses of the CWL model

- Resistance to innovation: the implementation of the CWL may encounter resistance from teachers, administrators, and parents who are accustomed to traditional teaching methods and may be hesitant to embrace change.
- Fear of creativity: some students and teachers may be hesitant to express themselves freely and share innovative ideas, which could limit the potential of the CWL.
- Time constraints: the CWL may require additional time for lesson preparation and activity management, which could be challenging for teachers and students to manage.

- Problem-solving difficulties: students may struggle with solving complex problems or problems without clear solutions, which could lead to frustration and confusion.
- Stakeholder involvement: ensuring the involvement of all stakeholders, such as teachers, parents, and students, can be a challenge, particularly if some individuals struggle to understand or adopt the new method.
- Implementation and training: implementing the CWL requires resources and adequate training for teachers, which could be a barrier in some schools and educational institutions.

The results of the survey and the reports of workshops conducted in IEXS for CWL model creation are attached in the appendix for the reference.

5 CWL Structure

5.1 Introduction

The results of IEXs endeavours were presented to the CREAM Consortium during the Second TPM, which took place in Warsaw, Poland, on the 9th and 10th of May 2023.

While the Consortium commended the in-depth analysis, some exceptions were raised with regards to a perceived lack of storytelling in the Model developed up to that point.

The following integration was developed as part of the PR3-A2 - "Development of training materials for Trainers and Students", submitted to the Consortium for feedback, and subsequently utilised as part of the training package for PR3-A3 "Training of the Trainers" activities, which ran in October 2023 as a first step towards the realisation of the CWL Pilots. The idea behind this integration was providing Trainers with simple, hands-on tools that can help teachers design and organise their CWL activities.

This first iteration of the Creative Writing Laboratory Model will be tested during the PR3-A5 "Pilot" Activities, scheduled to take place between February and July 2024, and eventually refined in the final stage of PRA2-A4 between June and August 2024.

5.2 Basic Elements

CREAM's CWLs are about combining the study of STEM subjects with creative writing.

You need 6 things to build your CWL:

- 1) an original idea
- 2) a problem to solve via a STEM subject
- 3) an activity organised around solving the problem
- 4) a story, to embed your activity into a narrative
- 5) a narration, to make the activity, the story and the solution visible
- 6) a conclusion, to show everybody what your students have achieved.

5.2.1 The Idea

The idea is what you would like your students to do with the CWL. Depending on how much time you have, you can finalise the details yourself or give your students a general outline of what you have in mind and ask them to flesh it out. The idea is made up of three parts:

- a narrative framework, which is a story inside of which the activities take place. It needs an element of conflict that will be resolved through the activity.
- a problem to solve, connected to the conflict in the story and to the practical, STEM-based activity
- a practical, STEM-based activity through which your students will solve the problem and simultaneously bring a solution to the conflict in the story.

5.2.2 The problem

Think of the problem as the junction between the narrative framework and the practical activities your students will participate in. Solving the problem will be both the

successful result of the activity and the solution necessary to the conflict in the narrative framework.

The STEM subject, or subjects, you choose to include should match your idea, and be the basis for the practical activities.

The Problem is where the Task and the Conflict meet. The solution your students will find is simultaneously the result of their task and the key to solving the conflict in the story. You can set up the problem in many ways, including:

- students need to choose between two or more options
- students have to invent, or discover, an original solution
- students have to overcome one or more challenges

5.2.3 The Activity

The activity, or activities, is what the students will do practically. The activity needs to be linked to the narrative framework and needs to involve at least one STEM subject.

When planning your activities, think about the following:

- the task your students need to perform
- the space they need
- the time allotted to them
- the materials they can use
- the external actors you'll need to involve
- the way you are going to evaluate the activity
- the schedule, which is:
 - when and how you will launch the activity
 - the logistics of the activity
 - how are you going to close the activity (a party, an event...)

- when and how you are going to collect feedback from students, teachers and parents.

The task links directly to the problem the students need to solve. By finding a solution, they will also solve the conflict within the story.

Your students should document the process of going through the set of activities, following the Guidelines provided as a result of PR4-A1 “Guidelines for creative contributions made by students during CWLs pilots”.

Once they have completed their task and have taken the story to a successful closure, your students need to make what they have done visible by going through the same steps you went through in planning the CWL: decide on a medium, write a script, and produce the content.

The final step is releasing the students output. It's the coronation of all their efforts, so make sure to make a big deal about it

5.2.4 The Story

The story acts as a framework, as a setting STEM-based activity. When you think about your story, you need to devise:

- a plot, in which your students take part
- characters your students can relate to
- a setting, to make the story believable
- a conflict in the story. The conflict is particularly important because it links directly to the Task of the practical activity. When your students perform their task successfully, they also find a solution to the conflict in the story.

- a resolution: this can be decided beforehand or you can give your students the option to invent one on their own, based on the activity they perform.

The diagram in the following page provides a schematic synthesis of the steps of the CWL creation and implementation.

5.3 CWL Diagram

5.4 CWL Checklist

3.1 Template

You can use this checklist to plan your CWL. Take a look at the guiding questions in the template, and work your idea until you are satisfied.

Make sure you check all the boxes and do take the time to plan everything very carefully. The more accurate your planning, the easier it will be to adapt and react to the unexpected.

Element	Detail	Descriptor	Done
1 Idea			
Title		the title of your CWL	
2 Problem			
Subject 1		What kind of problem is it	
Subject 2		What STEM subject(s) do your students need to solve it?	
Subject 3		How does it fit into the narrative of your story?	
3 Activity			
Task		what your students have to do or perform to find a solution to the Problem (connects to Conflict in "Story")	
Place		where the activity takes place	
Time		what time and for how long the activity lasts	
Materials		what your students can or must use to perform the task	
External Actors		whose help they need to perform the task	
Evaluation		how you are going to grade your students' performance	
Schedule	Launch	how you are launching the CWL (communication to families, school event, other...)	
	Main activity	start and end date	
	Closing	how you are going to close the activity (connects to Narration)	
	Feedback	how you are collecting feedback from all the involved parties	
4 Story			

Plot		what happens in the story	
Characters		the protagonists and antagonists of the story	
Setting		where and when the story takes place	
Conflict		the problem your student help the protagonists solve (connects to Task in "Activity")	
Resolution		what happens if the problem is solved	
5 Narration			
Media		students select a medium to tell their story	
Script		students work on the script / storyboard	
Output production		students produce the output	
Release		how you are showing the students' output (party, school event, online event...)	
6 Conclusion			
Closing		how you are going to close the activity (connects to Narration)	

3.2 Blank

It's your turn now. Let's get to work!

Element	Detail	Descriptor	Done
1 Idea			
Title			
2 Problem			
Subject 1			
Subject 2			
Subject 3			
3 Activity			
Task			
Place			
Time			
Materials			
External Actors			
Evaluation			
Schedule	Launch		
	Main activity		

	Closing		
	Feedback		
4 Story			
Plot			
Characters			
Setting			
Conflict			
Resolution			
5 Narration			
Media			
Script			
Output production			
Release			
6 Conclusion			
Closing			

5 Conclusions

The ideas, notions, aspirations, and hopes contained in this Deliverable will be put to the test during Piloting of the CWL courses, scheduled to take place between from February to July 2024. Feedback will be collected by means of an array of different strategies, from the Pilots' outputs to dedicated surveys. This wealth of data will be used to extract lessons learnt and best practices, with which the current CWL Model will be refined and validated in its final version, which is due to be released completed in by August 2024.

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